

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Long-term investigations of the impacts of catch crops in early potato farming is needed

Field case study experiment was carried out in early potato field in the boreal pedoclimatic region in Finland. Since the growing period of early potato in Finland is short, only 1.5-2 months, the soil remains bare for most of the year, making it prone to erosion. Therefore, early potato farmers would benefit from management practices that could prevent nutrient and carbon loss, as well as further damage. The potential of two different catch crops, phacelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia*) and a mixture of rye (*Secale cereale*) and Westerwolds ryegrass (*Lolium westermoldicum*), to prevent physical and chemical damage, nutrient and carbon loss, and to promote soil biological diversity in an early potato field. After 3-year monitoring period, from a socio-economic perspective, the short-term use of catch crops after harvest in boreal early potato farming cannot be recommended, since sowing catch crops results in additional

costs for farmers due to decreased gross margins. However, phacelia as a catch crop may have impact on the soil nitrogen cycle in early potato field. The farmer has the opportunity to utilise the environmental compensation system when growing phacelia as a catch crop after the harvest of early potatoes.

Changes in nematodes refer to the potentially beneficial effect of catch crops on pest and disease control in early potato field. Overall, long-term investigations are needed to verify the benefits of catch crops in boreal early potato field. More knowledge is needed on the species and varieties of catch crops, both cultivated individually and in mixtures, as well as on the methods for pest and disease control. It would be recommended to explore benefits of catch crops in more diverse crop rotations than in this case study.

1. *Phacelia tanacetifolia* as a catch crop flowering on Finnish early potato field.

KEYWORDS

Catch crop, Phacelia, rye, rye grass, early potato

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